

DESIRA: Digitisation: Economic and Social Impacts in Rural Areas

Deliverable 7.3: Ethical Guidelines

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Ethical Guidelines

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1. Introduction	1
2. Ethics requirements concerning DESIRA	2
2.1. Research involving Human beings	2
2.2. Protection of Personal Data.....	2
3. Ethics requirements and data collections in DESIRA.....	3
3.1. Work Package 1	3
3.2. Work Package 2	3
3.3. Work Package 3	4
3.4. Work Package 4	5
3.5. Work Package 5	5
3.6. Work Package 6	6
3.7. Work Package 7	7
4. Attachment 1 – information sheet	8
5. Attachment 2 – Informed Consent Form and privacy notice.....	8
6. Attachment 3 - Ethics Requirements for RRI compliance	10

1. Introduction

The DESIRA Project (Digitization: social and economic impact) aims at filling the socio-economic knowledge gaps on digitisation in agriculture, rural areas and forestry: to do this, DESIRA will assess the past and current socio-economic impact of digitisation in relation to Sustainable Development Goals, in order to improve the capacity of rural communities to reap the opportunities offered by digitisation and to improve resilience to related hazards by identifying and assessing existing policy instruments.

DESIRA develops a transdisciplinary methodology involving 20 territorial or subsector- based Living Labs, and an EU-level Rural Digitisation Forum, thus including in the research activity a wide range of EU citizens.

Deliverable 8.1 "H - requirement No. 1" (submitted) and Deliverable 8.2 "POPD – Requirement No.2" (due at month 12) deal with the ethics requirements that the project must comply with: this deliverable will integrate such documents by reporting the needs in terms of ethics in each Work Package, in order to advice Consortium partners on how to deal with the requirements concerning research involving human beings and Protection of Personal Data.

The Deliverable 7.3 aims to provide DESIRA Partners with specific guidelines on how to manage ethical issues in the activities foreseen by the Project. This document precedes any involvement of research participants external to the consortium, so that partners will have clear instruction on how to be compliant.

The document is organised as follow: after this short introduction, next chapter states the requirements for research involving human participants; chapter N.2 states the ethics requirements concerning DESIRA; chapter N.3 details the research activity to be carried out in each Work Package and the associated procedures and documents needed to satisfy the ethics requirements in accordance with EC procedures.

2. Ethics requirements concerning DESIRA

As reported in the Grant Agreement, the main ethical issues for DESIRA concerns Research involving Human beings and the Protection of Personal Data.

2.1. Research involving Human beings

DESIRA research activity will involve human beings, who will participate on a voluntary basis.

We will engage a large number of adult human participants involved in ICTs, agricultural, forestry and other rural sectors, as well as a wide range of stakeholders and experts engaged in the design and implementation of policies that focus on digitalisation in farming, forestry and rural areas. In relation to this, humans participating in DESIRA research could be: farmers, foresters, ICT businesses, rural entrepreneurs, advisors, stakeholders from NGOs, researchers as well as policy makers or staff members of administrative and financial agencies (both public and private).

Linked to the profile of research participants, main criteria to recruit them will be: their experience connected to digitalisation in agriculture, forestry and other rural activities, their professional expertise, their interest in DESIRA.

Moreover, DESIRA will not involve vulnerable groups, persons unable to give consent, children, patients or any other sensitive group and will not involve any physical or psychological interventions on participants.

Prior to the collection of any data, participants shall be informed on the collection, processing and use of data provided and contact persons of the Consortium will ensure that they give the consent.

Detailed procedures for gaining informed consent from research participants in the context of specific research activities will be described in chapter 3.

2.2. Protection of Personal Data

The research in DESIRA involves personal data collection and processing: these data need to be protected in compliance with the EU Regulation n. 2016/679, which defines personal data as “any information relating to an identified or identifiable person” (for full definition see art. 4).

Within DESIRA primary data will be collected (name, address, email, cv, phone number) through face-to-face interviews, phone calls, email and workshops; in Deliverable 8.1 and in Deliverable 7.2 “Data Management Plan” more details are provided about the processing of personal data within DESIRA. Potential research participants will be provided with clear information about the collection, processing, storage, breaching of their personal data and also on how to withdraw consent should they so wish.

3. Ethics requirements and data collections in DESIRA

All Work Packages in DESIRA are obliged to adhere by ethics requirements for collecting research and personal data. The following sub-chapters provide a description of the main research activity in each Work Package and provide details on the necessary steps to be compliant with Ethics requirements.

3.1. Work Package 1

Work Package 1 is the WP dedicated to the development of a shared knowledge and language among participants to the Project. It is going to provide definition of key concepts, to identify main research hypotheses, to develop key research questions and contributing to fill the knowledge gap about digitization. The objectives of WP1 are to develop an interdisciplinary and transdisciplinary conceptual and analytical framework and to develop a taxonomy and inventory of Digital Game Changers.

In order to reach the above mentioned objectives, research in WP1 requires interviews to be carried out with visionary people/experts. In task 1.1, a number of 5 interviews will be performed in order to check the Conceptual Framework, to be sure that all relevant aspects are covered and tested on real life cases.

In task 1.2, 20 interviews will be conducted in order to deepen and collect different view points about DGCs. These interviews will be recorded and videoclips will be produced for further communication activities.

Before starting the interview and the filming, the data collector will be required to inform the participant on the data collection, use and analysis of data provided and get the signed consent. The consent form - a document containing information on the project and the specific activity and how the data is used and stored and how withdrawal can be sought at any time without giving any reason (attachment 2) - shall be in a made available in native languages, or in easy to interpret text by the participant. The signed consent forms will be securely stored following the organisation's security guidelines.

Main implementation steps:

- Translation of the informed consent form in an understandable language for the research participant (if needed);
- Before starting the interview and the video recording obtain the signature on the informed consent form;
- After the interview, the signed form shall be stored securely on file, according to the organisation's security rules.

3.2. Work Package 2

Work Package 2 aims to assess past and present trends of digitalisation. Its objectives are to develop an inclusive approach to data collection and assessment of digitalisation consequences, to select (and validate) a set of socio-economic sustainability indicators (SESI) as well as a digitalisation index, to measure costs, benefits, trade-offs and gaps between societal needs, expectations and impacts (NEI).

Among the research activities aimed at reaching the objectives, this work package foresees to realise interviews to key informants, an on-line survey, a face-to-face workshop with Living Labs.

Before starting to gather information the data collectors are required to inform research participants on the collection, use and analysis of data provided and obtain the consent. The consent form (attachment 2) shall be in a completely understandable language by the participant and the signed consent forms will be securely stored following the organisation's security guidelines.

As interviews will chronologically precede the workshop, if an interviewee will be also participating in the workshop, the consent must be given only once.

The on-line survey will be realised by using a service provider GDPR compliant.

Main implementation steps:

- Translation of the informed consent form in an understandable/native language for the research participant (if needed);
- Before starting the interviews and the workshop, get the signature from each participant on the informed consent form;
- After the interviews and the workshop, signed forms shall be stored securely on file, according to the organisation's security rules.

3.3. Work Package 3

Work Package 3 deals with developing scenarios, use cases and showcase technologies, from the starting point that outcomes of future digitalisation will depend on the capacity of communities, researchers and innovators to anticipate their impacts. WP3 will work with the Living Labs to develop plausible future scenarios and identify desirable solutions to identified problems.

Among the research activities aimed at reaching the objectives, the WP3 foresees to organise two workshops in each of the 20 Living Labs, and an additional workshop in 5 of them to further develop Use Cases.

Before each workshop, the data collector is required to inform research participants on the collection, use and analysis of data provided and get the consent. The consent form (attachment 2) shall be in a completely understandable/native language by the participant and the signed consent forms will be securely stored following the organisation's security guidelines.

If a research participant will be participating to more than one workshop, the consent must be given only once.

Main implementation steps:

- Translation of the informed consent form in an understandable language for the research participant (if needed);
- Before starting the workshop(s), get the participants signature on the informed consent form;

- After the workshop(s), signed forms shall be stored securely on file, in accordance with the organisation's security guidelines.

3.4. Work Package 4

Work Package 4 title is "Policy roadmap and ethical code". WP4 main objective is to propose a Policy Roadmap which addresses the main obstacles and policy gaps identified and aligns the the Digital Game Changers in agriculture, forestry and rural life to societal needs. The Policy Roadmap will propose building blocks and policy pathways to support smart, inclusive and sustainable digitization of rural areas, with focus on integration of RRI approach and Sustainable Development Goals in the policy process.

Among the research activities aimed at reaching the objectives, the WP4 foresees 20 Policy Auditions in each of the 20 Living Labs, targeted at policy makers.

Before the Audition, the data collector is required to inform research participants on the collection, use and analysis of data provided and get the consent. The consent form (attachment 2) shall be in a completely understandable language by the participant and the signed consent forms will be securely stored following the organisation's security guidelines.

Main implementation steps:

- Translation of the informed consent form in an understandable language for the research participant (if needed);
- Before starting the meeting, get the signature of the informed consent by each participant;
- After the meeting, signed forms shall be stored securely on file, according to the organisation's security rules.

3.5. Work Package 5

Work Package 5 concerns the Knowledge infrastructure of DESIRA, aiming at fostering on-line interactions. Specific objectives of WP5 are to implement a Virtual Research Environment, to create a knowledge base for access to information on ICT tools and to develop an open-access Socio-economic assessment tool.

In this WP no data collection involving persons external to the Consortium is foreseen.

The DESIRA VRE is accessible via the portal d4science.org, which is GDPR compliant.

3.6. Work Package 6

Work Package 6 concerns the Dissemination, Exploitation, Communication and Outreach strategy of DESIRA. Its objectives relate to maximise the impact of project results and to manage the workplan of the RDF.

In this WP will be performed several activities involving and targeted to people external to the consortium, so it is interested by ethical issues, especially by the Regulation on Protection of Personal Data (GDPR).

Newsletter

The quarterly newsletter is aimed at the communication of project content, serving as a “reminder call” of the project to all subscribers. It provides project news and includes links to the DESIRA social media accounts, where subscribers are invited to join for quicker daily updates.

Rural Digitisation Forum (RDF)

The RDF is the DESIRA’s common platform for engagement and exchange set up at EU level. The RDF provides spaces and channels for the engagement and participation of stakeholders from across Europe in the research activities, development and dissemination of specific project’s outputs and products.

In practice, the RDF is built on a composite of physical and virtual platforms to ensure participation and engagement of the DESIRA community. The virtual platform will be developed in the VRE composed with experts from within DESIRA (and key external experts) and structured around four Working Groups. In addition, a private Facebook and a LinkedIn group (membership on request) will be permanently established as a base for the exchange of content and ideas, and provide the opportunity to get feedback from like-minded individuals from outside the DESIRA consortium.

The physical platform is represented by the 3 meetings of the RDF, which will be implemented by specific WP leaders (ILVO; UNIPI; HUTTON and UCO) and supported by AEIDL

The four RDF Working Groups (WGs) will be on:

- WG1: Digitisation of ‘agriculture’,
- WG2: Digitisation of ‘forestry’,
- WG3: Digitisation of ‘rural areas/life’
- WG4: Digitisation ‘policies’.

Each of the RDF WGs is composed by a limited number of experts (between 10-20 members) who are interested and willing to contribute with their knowledge in the research process and activities of DESIRA.

In addition, a specific call for experts could be launched within the general RDF to apply through an online form to be members of the RDF WG (Similarly to EIP-AGRI call for experts for Focus Groups).

Main implementation steps.

- Newsletter – use a mailing system GDPR compliant
- RDF mailing list – use a mailing system GDPR compliant

- RDF calls for experts for RDF WGs – use an on-line application form GDPR compliant
- RDF meetings and workshops - before the first face-to face meeting, the responsible partner for organising RDF meetings is required to inform participants on the collection, use and analysis of data provided, as well as on the video recording and get the consent prior to the meeting. The consent form (attachment 2) shall be in a completely understandable language by the participant and the signed consent forms will be securely stored following the organisation's security guidelines.
- RDF Community on Facebook and LinkedIn – The aim of this RDF engagement platforms is to provide stakeholders with a platform in which they can interact with each other, share experiences, events, articles, projects, proposals, initiatives, conferences etc. Facebook and LinkedIn (to a lesser extent), are social media platforms commonly used for this type of networking.
- Webinars: WGs will implement up to 4 webinars which could also be targeted to external people. This activity aims to enhance the knowledge of the group on a particular outstanding issue, concern, or topic which is also relevant to contribute to DESIRA outputs. These webinars will be recorded and published for external dissemination. Thus, the webinar will result in a video and possibly related articles which will be disseminated throughout the RDF.

If a RDF member will participate to more than one RDF workshop or meeting, he/she have to give the consent only once.

DESIRA final conference

The final conference will provide a synthesis of the main policy and practice-oriented findings of the project, serving to increase the visibility of the project, foster the exploitation of results, and present it to the general public, target groups and relevant stakeholders.

3.7. Work Package 7

Work Package 7 is the WP on Coordination and management of DESIRA and its objective is to ensure the achievement of the project objectives in a smooth and efficient way.

In this WP no data collection involving persons external to the Consortium is foreseen.

4. Attachment 1 - information sheet

DESIRA is a Horizon 2020 Project coordinated by the University of Pisa which involves 24 organisation (research institutes, NGOs, SMEs) in a multi-actor, inter-disciplinary Consortium.

The overarching goal of DESIRA is to improve the capacity of society and of political bodies to respond to the challenges that digitisation generates in rural areas, agriculture and forestry in the next ten years. To achieve this goal, we want to build a knowledge and methodological base that increases the capacity of a wide range of actors to assess past, current and future socio-economic impacts - included gender differences - of ICT's related innovation, to embody Responsible Research and Innovation into researchers', developers', users' practices and policies, and finally offer mechanisms and tools that will support decision-making to challenges and opportunities related to digitization.

Currently, there is a tendency that only the opportunities of digitisation are highlighted, while threats tend to be ignored or underestimated. DESIRA aims at closing the knowledge gap on the socio-economic impact of digitisation in agriculture, forestry and rural areas. It provides a comprehensive assessment of both opportunities and threats, taking the Sustainable Development Goals as a point of reference.

DESIRA will pursue its objectives by mobilizing a network of Rural businesses and services, Public Authorities, Citizen groups, Digital technology operators, Farmers, Media and Academics, organized into 20 Living Labs and one EU-level Rural Digitisation Forum.

Several interactive activities will be performed along the lifespan of the project, such as interviews, workshops, meetings. Participants will be asked to give their consent for the use, processing, storage and publication of data they provided to contribute to the research.

5. Attachment 2 - Informed Consent Form and privacy notice

Name and organisation of data collector: _____

Name of the research participant: _____

1) Consent statement

the research participant have been informed that:

- Data is being collected as part of the EU H2020 Project DESIRA.
- Data collected, audio recording, video-shooting and photos may be taken and used for research, dissemination and communication purposes.
- Data will be analysed by members of the DESIRA project, and in some cases may be analysed by project members other than the interviewer.
- Participation is voluntary.

- Consent can be withdrawn at any time without reason.
- Participants can access personal data at any time without reason.
- Data will be anonymised if possible. In cases in which the data cannot be anonymised, any publications will be shown to identifiable participants for further consent for publication.
- Data will be safely stored in certified repositories for long term preservation and curation.

Signed _____ (participant)
Date _____

2) Recording of consent
Project partners will keep evidence of consent by recording.

Name of the person who gained consent: _____

Data and time that consent was given: _____

PRIVACY NOTICE

The [Name of the Organisation] will use your personal data for the purposes of the research undertaken in the DESIRA project. Our legal basis for processing your data is that it is necessary for the performance of a task carried out in the public interest in relation to research funded by the European Commission, under Grant Agreement 818194.

We are the Data Controller over your personal data. We will not share your personal data beyond the project team, unless required by law and shall only retain it according to good scientific practice for as long as is necessary to fulfil the research undertaken on the project, to deliver project outcomes, and to fulfil the requirements of the funder. For further information, please contact our Data Protection Officer on [add email address of data protection officer]¹.

[Insert data collector name]

Contact details:

[Name of organisation]

[Address]

Email:

Telephone:

¹ If there is no privacy notice on the partner's website, and if a partner does not have a Data Protection Officer, substitute the sentence with the following: "For further information please contact [add email address of person responsible for data protection]."

6. Attachment 3 - Ethics Requirements for RRI compliance

Work Package 1 Conceptualising and mapping Digital Game changers

Title of Activity	Conceptual framework test interviews
Description of activity	N. 5 Interviews with practitioners, experts, academics, to make sure that in the Conceptual Framework all relevant aspects are covered and tested on the real life case.
Methods and measurement	<p>WP1 team will identify 5 experts, the experts will be approached to get an initial indication of their willingness to be interviewed, contact to be made by email.</p> <p>A time and place for the interview will be agreed with the expert. Before the interviews take place the participant will be informed verbally and given written text explaining the project, purpose of this interview and how the data will be stored and used. The participant must be given the opportunity to withdraw at anytime without explanation. This document requires a signature and will be the informed consent.</p> <p>These interviews may be recorded and the recording will be analysed for research purposes.</p>
Participants	Practitioners, experts, academics
Recruitment	Experts will be identified by WP1 team
Ethical Considerations checklist	<p>Provide information on the activity and the project both verbally and written, through an information sheet. Go through the following points:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The audio recordings and any reproduction shall remain the property of the author and that the DESIRA project may use the image as it sees fit. • The material will be used in a legitimate manner and is not intended to cause any harm or undue embarrassment to the parties involved • Check the interviewee has understood the information provided and that they understand they have the opportunity to withdraw at any time.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ensure that consent is given to use the interviewee's image, voice or both by the project, signature required.
Information provided to participants	Information about DESIRA, and protection of data and personal data provided.
Informed consent requested	Yes

Work Package 1 Conceptualising and mapping Digital Game changers

Title of Activity	Interviews with visionary experts
Description of activity	20 Interviews with visionary people/experts in order to deepen and collect different view points about DGCs
Methods and measurement	Partners will identify 2 experts, the experts will be approached to get an initial indication of their willingness to be interviewed, contact to be made by email. Partners to complete the on-line expert survey. The leader of task 1.2 will check and help select the most appropriate expert for each partner to interview. A time and place for the interview will be agreed with the expert. Before the interviews take place the participant will be informed verbally and given written text explaining the project, purpose of this interview and how the data will be stored and used. The participant must be given the opportunity to withdraw at anytime without explanation. This document requires a signature and will be the informed consent. These interviews will be recorded and videoclips will be produced for further communication activities. The videoclips will be shared prior to being made publicly available.
Participants	Experts in digital technology, stakeholders
Recruitment	Partners will identify the experts, the experts will be approached by email to ask for their willingness to be interviewed.
Ethical Considerations checklist	Provide information on the activity and the project both verbally and written, through an information sheet. Go through the following points: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The video and/or audio recordings and any reproduction shall remain the property of the author and that the DESIRA project may use the image as it sees fit. The images may appear publicly as part of the project website, social media communications and/or other marketing materials related to the project.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The material will be used in a legitimate manner and is not intended to cause any harm or undue embarrassment to the parties involved Check the interviewee has understood the information provided and that they understand they have the opportunity to withdraw at any time. Ensure that consent is given to use the interviewee's image, voice or both by the project, signature required.
Information provided to participants	Information about DESIRA, the aim of the interview, the protection of data and personal data provided.
Informed consent requested	Video Audio Photographs

Work Package 2 Assessing past and present impact

Title of Activity	Task 2.4: Online questionnaire
Description of activity	The online questionnaire will collect additional information on the current reaching of SDGs, the conditions, expectations as well as costs- benefit of digitisation. The survey will addressed he stakeholders already involved in LL.
Methods and measurement	The questionnaire will be submitted by sharing with stakeholder the link to the survey and will contains some personal information and opinions about digitisation and business activities. The participant must be given the opportunity to withdraw at anytime without explanation. Data will be stored as dataset and they will be analysed in aggregated way.
Participants	The on-line survey will be filled by participants of LLs.
Recruitment	Participants will be identified by key informant interviews.
Ethical Considerations checklist	Provide information on the activity and the project both verbally and written, through an information sheet. Go through the following points: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The material will be used in a legitimate manner and is not intended to cause any harm or undue embarrassment to the parties involved

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ensure that consent is given if personnel data is to be collected and stored.
Information provided to participants	Work Package Leaders to give details
Informed consent requested	Yes

Work Package 2 Assessing past and present impact

Title of Activity	Task 2.4: Needs, expectation and impact appraisal
Description of activity	Living Lab workshop and Interviews
Methods and measurement	<p>Using the guidelines developed in 2.1 the WP2 will apply ARDI method to create a describe and represent LL as well as Bayesian Belief Network to measure impact of digitisation.</p> <p>All participants in the workshop need to sign an informed consent form for the workshop as well as to share video and photo to the social and project website.</p> <p>The 5-10 key informants to be interviewed will need a more detailed consent form including the possibility of recording.</p> <p>All participants must be given the opportunity to withdraw at anytime without explanation.</p> <p>Task leader will store data collected in the VRE in the own computer and make available descriptive statistics. Data will be shared only after publication on peer-review journal and after an embargo period.</p>
Participants	Stakeholders
Recruitment	Partners will identify the stakeholders through the key informants; the participants of the Living Lab will be invited by partners
Ethical Considerations checklist	<p>Provide information on the activity and the project both verbally and written, through an information sheet. Go through the following points:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The images may appear publicly as part of the project website, social media communications and/or other marketing materials related to the project. The material will be used in a legitimate manner and is not intended to cause any harm or undue embarrassment to

	<p>the parties involved</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Check the interviewee has understood the information provided and that they understand they have the opportunity to withdraw at any time. • Ensure that consent is given to use the interviewee's image, voice or both by the project, signature required.
Information provided to participants	Work Package Leaders to give details at the beginning of the survey.
Informed consent requested	Audio Photographs

Work Package 3 Developing scenarios, Use cases and showcase technologies

Title of Activity	Task 3.2 Living Lab scenario Workshop
Description of activity	Scenario workshops will be held with the LL members to discuss the future. Digital stories will be developed to form the narratives
Methods and measurement	<p>LL members should largely be the same as in task 2.4. The participants are invited to attend these 2 workshops to develop the scenarios and create digital stories.</p> <p>The participant will be informed verbally and given written text explaining the project, purpose of this workshop and how the data will be created, stored and used. The participant must be given the opportunity to withdraw at anytime without explanation. This document requires a signature and will be the informed consent.</p>
Participants	LL members
Recruitment	LL members will be invited to attend by email, by phone and via the dedicated VRE.
Ethical Considerations checklist	<p>Participation in workshop, the same informed consent from task 2.4 can be used for new participants, digital stories will require a separate consent if they include images owned by participants. Stock images need copyright permission or common copyrights. Provide information on the activity and the project both verbally and written, through an information sheet. Go through the following points:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The video and/or audio recordings and any reproduction shall remain the property of the author and that the DESIRA project may use the image as it sees fit.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The images may appear publicly as part of the project website, social media communications and/or other marketing materials related to the project. • The material will be used in a legitimate manner and is not intended to cause any harm or undue embarrassment to the parties involved • Check the participant has understood the information provided and that they understand they have the opportunity to withdraw at any time. • Ensure that consent is given to use the participants image, voice or both by the project, signature required.
Information provided to participants	Participants will be provided with information about DESIRA, its aims, the purpose of the workshops through the information sheet.
Informed consent requested	Personal data Video Audio Photographs

Work Package 4 Policy roadmap and ethical code

Title of Activity	Policy auditions
Description of activity	During the living Labs the policy makers will be asked to validate the scenario report by discussing and refining
Methods and measurement	<p>LL members should largely be the same as in tasks 2.4. and 3.2</p> <p>The participants will be informed verbally and given written text explaining the project, purpose of this workshop and how the data will be stored and used. The participant must be given the opportunity to withdraw at anytime without explanation. This document requires a signature and will be the informed consent.</p> <p>The team responsible of the policy auditions will use the same method that in the previous LL workshops. Interventions may be voice or image recorded in order to prepare the final report. The report will be publicly available in order to feed other parts of the project. Data will be securely stored following the organisation's security guidelines.</p>
Participants	LL members and policy makers

Recruitment	They will receive a personal email, but all the information will be also available in the gate keeper.
Ethical Considerations checklist	<p>Participation in workshop, the same informed consent from task 2.4 and 3.2 can be used for new participants. Go through the following points:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The material will be used in a legitimate manner and is not intended to cause any harm or undue embarrassment to the parties involved • Check the participant has understood the information provided and that they understand they have the opportunity to withdraw at any time. • Ensure that consent is given to use the participants image, voice or both by the project, signature required.
Information provided to participants	Participants will be informed about the results of the previous LL discussions and will receive the scenario analysis report including the potential scenarios they need to discuss about.
Informed consent requested	<p>Video</p> <p>Audio</p> <p>Photographs</p>

Work Package 6 Exploitation, Dissemination, Communication and Outreach

Title of Activity	Newsletter
Description of activity	<p>Partners will provide content including: writing articles; suggest links to interesting articles; provide dates for events</p> <p>This information will be used to compile a newsletter that will be shared via a group email database</p>
Methods and measurement	<p>Interested partners are asked to register via a link to receive the newsletter. A confirmation email is sent and a link needs to be activated to confirm consent to receive the newsletter and be added to the data base.</p> <p>Information about the storage and processing of the data will be available in the Privacy Policy (accessible in the website www.desira2020.eu)</p>
Participants	Registered recipients (general audience)
Recruitment	Embedded form in the website

	Link through social media
Ethical Considerations checklist	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Personal data will be asked for and stored securely • The material will be used in a legitimate manner and is not intended to cause any harm or undue embarrassment to the parties involved • Recipients consent will be collected via a confirmation e-mail • Recipients will be able to consult the Privacy Policy at DESIRA’s website (www.desira2020.eu) <p>Recipients have the opportunity to withdraw at any time without an explanation (an email address will be provided)</p>
Information provided to participants	<p>Newsletter form (automatically generated by MailChimp)</p> <p>Privacy policy available in desira2020.eu</p>
Informed consent requested	Yes

Work Package 6 Exploitation, Dissemination, Communication and Outreach

Title of Activity	RDF – mailing list
Description of activity	<p>Partners will provide content including: writing articles; suggest links to interesting articles; provide dates for events</p> <p>This information will be used to compile a series of updates that will be shared via a group email database</p>
Methods and measurement	<p>Interested partners are asked to register via a link to receive the updates. A confirmation email is sent and a link needs to be activated to confirm consent to receive the e-mails and be added to the data base</p> <p>Information about the storage and processing of the data will be available in the Privacy policy (accessible in the website www.desira2020.eu)</p>
Participants	Registered recipients (general audience)
Recruitment	<p>Embedded form in the website</p> <p>Link through social media</p>
Ethical Considerations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Personal data will be asked for and stored securely. • The material will be used in a legitimate manner and is not

checklist	<p>intended to cause any harm or undue embarrassment to the parties involved</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Recipients consent will be collected via a confirmation e-mail • Recipients will be able to consult the Privacy Policy at DESIRA’s website (www.desira2020.eu) • Recipients have the opportunity to withdraw at any time without an explanation (an email address will be provided)
Information provided to participants	<p>Newsletter form (automatically generated by MailChimp)</p> <p>Privacy policy available in desira2020.eu</p>
Informed consent requested	Yes

Work Package 6 Exploitation, Dissemination, Communication and Outreach

Title of Activity	Call for RDF WGs experts
Description of activity	Prospective RDF members having indicated their interest in actively participating in the different activities will be given the opportunity to express their interest in engaging further in specific activities of the project (e.g. RDF Working Group, RDF meetings, Living Lab, or others, with final participation in those activities subject of confirmation on the basis of objective criteria.
Methods and measurement	<p>A specific call for experts to be members of the RDF WG will be launched within the RDF, which they can apply for through an online application form (e.g. Google Forms)</p> <p>Experts will be informed about the project, the duration of the data storage, the purpose of the registration and how the data will be stored and used</p> <p>Information about the storage and processing of the data will be accessible in the Privacy Policy (available in the website www.desira2020.eu)</p>
Participants	Stakeholders experts
Recruitment	<p>E-mail invitation. Only for experts with a particular interest in the project who have expressed their interest in the project beforehand</p> <p>Open call through an advertised link. We will use an on-line application form that is GDPR compliant (e.g. Google Forms)</p>

Ethical Considerations checklist	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Personal data will be asked for and stored securely • Experts will be able to consult the Privacy Policy at DESIRA's website (www.desira2020.eu) • Experts have the opportunity to withdraw at any time without an explanation (an email address will be provided)
Information provided to participants	Application form Privacy policy integrated as Annex
Informed consent requested	Yes

Work Package 6 Exploitation, Dissemination, Communication and Outreach

Title of Activity	Rural Digitization Forum (RDF) Meetings
Description of activity	<p>Face to face meetings will be developed around plenary sessions and working groups and will be facilitated to maximize the interaction. A total of 35 participants will engage in each of the meetings. The composition of the participants will reflect a balance of relevant stakeholders.</p> <p>Each WG will implement 1-2 virtual meetings. These will be done as webinars on a topic relevant for the group. This activity aims to enhance the knowledge of the group on a particular outstanding issue, concern, or topic which is also relevant to contribute to DESIRA outputs. These webinars will be recorded and published for external dissemination.</p>
Methods and measurement	<p>Among the RDF members interested in actively participating in DESIRA, the most relevant experts will be selected to participate at the face to face and virtual meetings.</p> <p>They will be asked to register through an online form (e.g. Google Forms), where they will be properly informed about the project, the data collection method and its purpose, the duration of the data storage and the type of data that will be generated.</p> <p>They will be asked to confirm understanding and consent of all the above in the registration form</p> <p>Information about the storage and processing of the data will be provided in the Privacy policy (available in the website www.desira2020.eu)</p>
Participants	Experts in digital technology, relevant stakeholders

Recruitment	Experts invited by on-line registration form that is GDPR compliant (e.g. Google Forms)
Ethical Considerations checklist	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The video and/or audio recordings and any reproduction shall remain the property of the author and that the DESIRA project may use the image as it sees fit. • The images may appear publicly as part of the project website, social media communications and/or other marketing materials related to the project. • The material will be used in a legitimate manner and is not intended to cause any harm or undue embarrassment to the parties involved • Ensure that consent is given to use the participant's image, voice or both by the project, signature required.
Information provided to participants	Registration + Consent form Privacy policy integrated as Annex
Informed consent requested	Yes

Work Package 6 Exploitation, Dissemination, Communication and Outreach

Title of Activity	RDF Webinars (4)
Description of activity	Each Working Group will implement 1-2 webinars on a topic relevant for the group. The WG will identify the relevant subjects, experts and questions for the discussion during the webinar. These webinars will be recorded and published for external dissemination, and will result in a video and possibly related articles which will be disseminated throughout the RDF. The webinar may take the form of a training on a relevant subject.
Methods and measurement	<p>Among the members of each Working Group, we will circulate an invitation to participate in the webinar.</p> <p>They will be asked to register through an online form (e.g. Google Forms), where they will be properly informed about the data collection method and its purpose, the duration of the data storage, the type of data that will be generated and for what will it be used.</p> <p>They will be asked to confirm understanding and consent of all the above in the registration form.</p>

	<p>When open to external actors, confirmation of registration will be subject to approval by the DESIRA team.</p> <p>Information about the storage and processing of the data will be provided in the Privacy policy (available in the website www.desira2020.eu)</p>
Participants	Stakeholders experts (eventually open to other relevant actors)
Recruitment	Experts invited by on-line registration form that is GDPR compliant (e.g. Google Forms)
Ethical Considerations checklist	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The video and/or audio recordings and any reproduction shall remain the property of the author and the DESIRA project may use the image as it sees fit • The images may appear publicly as part of the project website, social media communications and/or other marketing materials related to the project. • The material will be used in a legitimate manner and is not intended to cause any harm or undue embarrassment to the parties involved • Ensure that consent is given to use the participant's image, voice or both by the project (signature of registration form required)
Information provided to participants	<p>Registration + Consent form</p> <p>Privacy policy integrated as Annex</p>
Informed consent requested	Yes

Work Package 6 Exploitation, Dissemination, Communication and Outreach

Title of Activity	DESIRA final conference
Description of activity	The final conference will provide a synthesis of the main policy and practice-oriented findings of the project, serving to increase the visibility of the project, foster the exploitation of results, and present it to the general public, target groups and relevant stakeholders.
Methods and measurement	A public invitation will be made available through the website and publicise via the different DESIRA communication channels. Attendees will be asked to register through an online form (e.g. Google Forms), where they will be properly informed about the data collection method and its purpose, the duration of the data

	<p>storage, the type of data that will be generated and for what will it be used.</p> <p>They will be asked to confirm understanding and consent of all the above in the registration form.</p> <p>Confirmation of registration will be subject to approval by the DESIRA team.</p> <p>Information about the storage and processing of the data will be provided in the Privacy policy (available in the website www.desira2020.eu)</p>
Participants	General public, target groups and general stakeholders
Recruitment	Stakeholders to fill out an on-line registration form that is GDPR compliant (e.g. Google Forms)
Ethical Considerations checklist	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The video and/or audio recordings and any reproduction shall remain the property of the author and the DESIRA project may use the image as it sees fit • The images may appear publicly as part of the project website, social media communications and/or other marketing materials related to the project. • The material will be used in a legitimate manner and is not intended to cause any harm or undue embarrassment to the parties involved • Ensure that consent is given to use the participant's image, voice or both by the project (signature of registration form required)
Information provided to participants	Registration + Consent form Privacy policy integrated as Annex
Informed consent requested	Yes